

Static and dynamic testing and design methods for driven piles in multilayered soil

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ABSTRACT

This paper summarizes the results of static and dynamic pile load tests performed on fully instrumented, driven piles in Indiana. The soil profiles at the test site locations consist of multiple layers of soils that are typical of alluvial deposits found at bridge sites. In most of the cases considered, closed-ended and open-ended pipe piles were driven side-by-side and tested to allow a comparison of the resistances mobilized in each layer of the soil profile and at the bases of the piles. For robustness and redundancy of the measurements, the piles were instrumented with a dense arrangement of electrical-resistance and vibrating-wire strain gauges along the entire length of the piles. The open-ended pipe piles were specially built with a double-wall system to allow separation of the internal and external resistances. Slow-maintained static load test protocols were followed to obtain the pile load-settlement curves with appropriate stiffness values. The tests were performed to large pile head settlements to allow determination of ultimate loads. Dynamic load tests were also performed to assess their ability to predict static resistances. The results of these tests were compared with predictions made using recent hybrid CPT-based design methods and pile driving formulas applied to measured sets during driving. An assessment of the methods of prediction or verification of ultimate resistances is made based on the results.

Keywords: instrumented pile load test, pile driving formula, pile design method, pile resistance, case histories

1 INTRODUCTION

Static and dynamic load tests are often performed to determine the load-carrying capacity of the foundations of transportation infrastructure and high-rise structures. When proof or verification static load tests (SLTs) are performed, the instrumentation scheme is basic, consisting mainly of a load cell at the pile head to measure axial loads and vertical displacement instruments to measure axial displacements during testing. Fully instrumented static pile load tests, which are usually performed in the context of research projects, yield valuable data for the validation and development of design methods based on either *in situ* soil test data or soil properties and for the validation of analysis results (Fellenius et al., 2004; Gavin and Lehane, 2003; Han et al., 2019c; Jardine et al., 2005; Jardine 2020; Kikuchi et al., 2007). Instrumentation schemes used in research include the installation of electrical-resistance (ER) and/or vibrating-wire (VW) strain gauges along the length of the pile, on opposite sides of the cross-section of the pile, to measure the strains at those locations (from which the stresses and forces can be calculated by

knowing the Young's modulus and the cross-sectional area of the pile) as the load test progresses (Bica et al., 2014; Ganju et al., 2020, 2021; Han et al., 2017, 2018, 2019a,b, 2020a,b; Kim et al., 2009; Paik et al., 2003; Seo et al., 2009). In this manner, the load transferred to the ground between two consecutive instrumented cross sections of a pile can be obtained at each stage of loading. Fully instrumented pile load tests allow determination of both the shaft and base resistances of the pile.

Dynamic load testing and monitoring rely on data collected during a hammer blow from accelerometers and strain transducers attached to the pile head (Salgado et al., 2017a). In addition to these commonly used instrumentation schemes, instrumentation of bridge piers and their foundations allow the measurement of dead and live loads, the load transferred from the superstructure to each pile in pile groups, the load carried by pile caps, and the settlement of individual piers and bents, thus enabling checks on design assumptions and calculations done in design (Han et al., 2020c, 2021; Raja et al., 2022). Details on pile load testing, planning, and

instrumentation procedures are provided in Paik et al. (2003), Bica et al. (2014), and Han et al. (2017, 2019a,b).

Several cone penetration test (CPT)-based pile design methods, such as the Purdue Pile Design Method (PPDM) (Han et al., 2017, 2019a; Randolph, 2003; Salgado, 2022; Salgado et al., 2011), the Imperial College Pile Design Method (ICPDM) (Jardine et al., 2005), the University of Western Australia Pile Design Method (UWAPDM) (Lehane, 2019; Lehane et al., 2005, 2013), the Norwegian Geotechnical Institute Pile Design Method (NGIPDM) (Clausen et al., 2005; Karlsrud et al., 2005), and the Fugro Pile Design Method (FPDM) (Kolk and van der Velde, 1996; Kolk et al., 2005; Van Dijk and Kolk, 2010), have been developed for calculation of the axial capacity of driven piles—including closed-ended pipe (CEP) piles, open-ended pipe (OEP) piles and H-piles—in sand and clay. In general, these design methods were developed mostly based on pile load test data (complemented by results of finite element analyses in the case of the PPDM) and predict the ultimate load capacity Q_{ult} (usually defined as the capacity corresponding to a pile head settlement w equal to 10% of the pile diameter B) of a pile some time after installation (e.g., the ICPDM predicts the value of Q_{ult} for driven piles in sand 10 days after installation).

Setup factors have been proposed to account for the increase in capacity of piles in clay over time due to excess pore pressure dissipation (Basu et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2010). Friction degradation due to pile driving is accounted for by introducing a degradation function (e.g., an exponential function or a power function) on shaft resistance equations; maximum shaft resistance degradation is observed near the pile head, where soil experiences the largest number of cycles during driving (Lehane et al., 1993; Randolph et al., 1994; White and Lehane, 2004). Shaft resistance degradation is minimum near the pile base (Gavin and O’Kelly, 2007). A summary of the design equations and shaft resistance degradation functions involved in the PPDM, ICPDM, UWAPDM, NGIPDM, and FPDM can be found in Han et al. (2017), Gavin et al. (2021), Sakleshpur et al. (2021a), and Salgado (2022).

One of the tools that engineers often use to assess whether a pile, after installation, will have the required design capacity are the pile driving formulas. Pile driving formulas, which relate the pile set resulting from a hammer blow to the static load capacity of the pile, have been used extensively due to their simplicity and economic advantages (Salgado and Zhang, 2012). Traditional pile driving formulas, such as the Gates formula (Gates, 1957), the Modified ENR formula (ENR, 1965), the Danish formula (Olson and Flaate, 1967), the Pacific Coast Uniform Building Code (PCUBC) formula (Bowles, 1996), and the Janbu formula (Bowles, 1996) do not explicitly account for the soil type (e.g., sand or clay) surrounding the pile and the pile type (e.g., floating pile or end-bearing pile). To

address this shortcoming, Salgado et al. (2017b) used an advanced, nonlinear soil reaction model for dynamic pile driving analysis (Salgado et al., 2015) to develop pile driving formulas for different cases: floating piles in clay, piles in uniform sand deposits, end-bearing piles in sand, end-bearing piles in clay, and piles crossing soft clay and bearing on sand. A summary of the equations involved in the above pile driving formulas can be found in Salgado et al. (2017a,b).

In this paper, we discuss the results of static and dynamic load tests performed on fully instrumented piles driven in multilayered soil profiles in Indiana, USA. The SLTs were performed following slow-maintained testing protocols to obtain the load versus displacement curves representative of the test sites. Load-transfer curves obtained from the measurements made by the strain gauges installed along the length of the piles allowed a direct comparison between the measured and predicted unit shaft resistances in different soil layers of the profiles at the test sites. An assessment of the performance of various CPT-based pile design methods, dynamic load tests (DLTs), and pile driving formulas was made by comparing the predicted versus measured ultimate loads.

2 ULTIMATE LOAD CAPACITY OF PILE

The ultimate load capacity Q_{ult} of an axially loaded pile is the sum of the limit shaft capacity Q_{sL} and the ultimate base capacity $Q_{b,ult}$ of the pile (Sakleshpur et al., 2021a,b; Salgado 2022):

$$Q_{ult} = Q_{b,ult} + Q_{sL} = q_{b,ult} A_b + \sum_{i=1}^n q_{sLi} A_{si} \quad (1)$$

where q_{sLi} = limit unit shaft resistance of the pile segment in contact with layer i , A_{si} = circumferential area of the pile shaft interfacing with layer i , n = number of soil layers in contact with the pile shaft, $q_{b,ult}$ = ultimate unit base resistance, and A_b = area of the pile base. At a settlement level of $0.1B$, the shaft resistance of the pile is fully mobilized, but the base resistance of the pile may not be fully mobilized.

3 CASE HISTORIES

Several SLTs and DLTs were performed on various types of driven piles (CEP piles, OEP piles, and H-piles) at four different locations in Indiana, USA. The test site for the first pile load test (Paik et al., 2003) was located on state road 9 in Lagrange County; the test site for the second pile load test (Bica et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2009; Seo et al., 2009) was located on state road 49 in Jasper County; the test site for the third pile load test (Han et al., 2017, 2018) was located at the intersection of 7th road and U.S. 31 in Marshall County; and the fourth pile load test (Ganju et al., 2020, 2021; Han et al., 2019a,b, 2020a,b) was performed at the intersection of the east bank of the Wabash River with Sagamore Parkway in

Tippecanoe County. In addition to these pile load tests, other pile load test databases available in the literature include the NGI database (Clausen et al., 2005; Karlsrud et al., 2005; NGI, 2000, 2001), the Fugro database (Kolk and van der Velde, 1996; Kolk et al., 2005; Van Dijk and Kolk, 2010), the ICP database (Chow, 1997; Jardine and Chow, 1996; Jardine et al., 2005), the UWA database (Lehane et al., 2005, 2013; Schneider et al., 2008), the ZJU-ICL database (Yang et al., 2015, 2017), the unified database (Lehane et al., 2017), and the FHWA deep foundation load test database (version 2.0) (Machairas et al., 2018; Petek et al., 2016).

3.1 Lagrange County, Indiana

Table 1 summarizes the properties of the soil layers at the test site in Lagrange County; the soil profile consists of 3 m of loose gravelly sand ($D_R = 30\%$) followed by 10–11 m of dense gravelly sand ($D_R = 80\%$). The gravelly sand was underlain by stiff till containing silts and clays. The groundwater table was located at a depth of 3 m below the ground surface. Approximately 2 m of fill and pavement material was removed prior to pile installation and testing such that the soil layers were overconsolidated. Fig. 1 shows the q_c profiles obtained from two CPT soundings, C1 and C2, performed at the locations of the CEP and OEP piles, respectively. The profile of the overconsolidation ratio (OCR) is presented in Paik and Salgado (2003).

Table 1. Soil profile at the test site in Lagrange County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2017, 2019c; Paik et al., 2003).

z (m)	Layer description	γ_m (kN/m ³)	e_{max} (—)	e_{min} (—)	D_R (%)	ϕ_c (°)
0-3	Gravelly sand	16.38	0.68	0.41	30	33.3
3-13	Gravelly sand	21.20	0.68	0.41	80	33.3

Note: z = depth from the ground surface, γ_m = unit weight, e_{max} = maximum void ratio, e_{min} = minimum void ratio, D_R = relative density, and ϕ_c = critical-state friction angle.

The test piles consisted of a closed-ended, steel, pipe pile (with an outer diameter B of 356 mm and a wall thickness of 12.7 mm) and an open-ended, steel, pipe pile with the same outer diameter as that of the closed-ended pile. The OEP pile was composed of two pipes: an outer pipe with $B = 356$ mm and an inner pipe with $B = 305$ mm; both pipes had the same wall thickness of 6.4 mm. The CEP and OEP piles were driven using an ICE-42S single-acting diesel hammer, with a ram weight of 18.2 kN and a maximum hammer stroke of 3.12 m, down to depths of 6.87 m and 7.04 m, respectively, from the ground surface. The center-to-center distance between the CEP and OEP piles was about 4.9 m. The incremental filling ratio (IFR) and plug length ratio (PLR) were measured continuously during OEP pile driving using a system of two weights connected to each other by a steel wire; the heavier weight was placed on the surface of the soil plug while the lighter weight was allowed to hang freely outside the pile [further details can be found in Paik et al. (2003)]. The values of the IFR

and PLR at the end of OEP pile driving were 0.775 and 0.82, respectively.

Fig. 1. q_c profiles at the test site in Lagrange County, Indiana (after Paik et al., 2003).

The shaft of the CEP pile was instrumented with 9 pairs of ER strain gauges; the spacing between the gauges was decreased near the pile base to capture the greater load transfer in that region. For the double-wall OEP pile, the shafts of the inner and outer pipes were instrumented with 10 pairs and 9 pairs, respectively, of ER strain gauges. The gauges were protected against moisture intrusion and covered with an angled steel plate to prevent damage during pile driving.

DLTs were performed on the CEP and OEP piles both during driving and during a restrike performed 8 days after completion of the SLTs. Two strain transducers and two piezoelectric accelerometers were attached to the outside wall of the CEP pile and to the inside wall of the OEP pile. The capacities of both piles were estimated based on signal matching analysis using CAPWAP. The SLTs were performed 3 days after the end of pile driving. For the SLT, the piles were axially loaded using a hydraulic jack placed between the test pile head and the reaction beam. A load cell was used to measure the loads applied to the pile head. Pile head settlements were measured using two dial gauges attached to reference beams. The piles were loaded in increments of 147 kN; the load increment was decreased to 49–98 kN near the end of the test. Each load increment was maintained until the settlement rate of the pile head was less than 0.5 mm/hr. During each load step, pile head settlements were recorded at 5, 15, 35, 55, 75, 95, and 120 min.

For the OEP pile, the ultimate load Q_{ult} corresponding to a pile head settlement w of $0.1B$ (35.6 mm) was 1025 kN from the SLT, with shaft, base, plug, and annulus

capacities (without correction for residual loads) of 310 kN, 715 kN, 265 kN, and 450 kN, respectively. CAPWAP predictions based on the restrrike test indicated shaft, base, and total capacities of 454 kN, 823 kN, and 1277 kN, respectively, for the OEP pile. In contrast, for the CEP pile, the value of Q_{ult} at $w = 0.1B$ (35.6 mm) was 1499 kN from the SLT, with shaft and base capacities (without correction for residual loads) of 633 kN and 866 kN, respectively. CAPWAP predictions based on the restrrike test indicated shaft, base, and total capacities of 151 kN, 752 kN, and 903 kN, respectively, for the CEP pile.

Fig. 2 compares the limit unit shaft resistance q_{sL} profile of the CEP pile obtained from the SLT with those predicted using different CPT-based pile design methods. The axial loads were not corrected for residual loads due to uncertainties in the strain gauge measurements caused by drifts in the zero readings of the strain gauges. The PPDM, ICPDM, and UWAPDM produce consistent predictions of q_{sL} when compared to the measured values. Table 2 compares the ultimate base capacity $Q_{b,ult}$ of the CEP pile obtained from the SLT with those predicted by the pile design methods. The predictions of the PPDM and ICPDM are in good agreement with the measured value.

Fig. 2. Comparison of q_{sL} profiles obtained from the CEP pile load test (not correcting for residual loads) in Lagrange County, Indiana, with those predicted using (a) PPDM, (b) ICPDM, (c) UWAPDM, (d) NGIPDM, and (e) FPDM (Han et al., 2017).

Table 2. Comparison between predicted and measured base capacities of CEP pile in Lagrange County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2017, 2019c).

Test/design method	Value (kN)
SLT ($w = 0.1B$)	866 ^a
PPDM	881
ICPDM	826
UWAPDM	987
NGIPDM	786
FPDM	1088

^a Not corrected for residual load.

Table 3. Comparison between measured SLT capacity and capacities predicted using pile driving formulas for CEP pile in Lagrange County, Indiana (after Salgado et al., 2017b).

Test/pile driving formula	Value (kN)
SLT ($w = 0.1B$)	1499
Salgado et al. (2017b) formula ($w = 0.1B$)	1671
CAPWAP	903
Gates formula	1016
Modified ENR formula	3651
Danish formula	2744
PCUBC formula	2342
Janbu formula	2302

Table 3 compares the measured SLT capacity of the CEP pile with capacities predicted using different pile driving formulas available in the literature. The ultimate load capacity Q_{ult} of the pile estimated using the Salgado et al. (2017b) formula is 1671 kN, which is 11% greater than that obtained from the SLT. The CAPWAP prediction (based on a restrrike test performed 11 days after the end of pile driving) and the Gates formula are

conservative by 40% and 32%, respectively. In contrast, the ratios of the pile capacity estimated by the Janbu, PCUBC, Danish, and Modified ENR formulas to that obtained from the SLT are about 1.5, 1.6, 1.8, and 2.4, respectively.

3.2 Jasper County, Indiana

Table 4 summarizes the properties of the soil layers at the test site in Jasper County; the soil profile consists of multiple layers of sand, silt and clay; each layer has different percentages of these three soil types. Fig. 3 shows the q_c profiles obtained from two CPT soundings, C3 and C4, performed near the location of the H-pile load test. In addition, two CPT soundings, C1 and C2, were performed near the location of the CEP pile load test; the q_c profiles obtained from these soundings can be found in Kim et al. (2009). The CPT soundings C3 and C4 were terminated at a depth of about 18 m from the ground surface and 1 m into a very dense, nonplastic silt layer having a cone resistance of about 50 MPa. The very dense silt layer was underlain by a 7.6-m-thick soft silty clay layer, with a cone resistance of about 1.5 MPa. The groundwater table and bedrock were located at depths of 1 m and 26 m, respectively, from the ground surface.

Table 4. Soil profile at the test site in Jasper County, Indiana (after Seo et al., 2009).

z (m) ^a	Layer description	γ_m (kN/m ³)	PI (%)	ϕ_c (°)	OCR (—)	s_u (kPa)
0.0-1.6	Organic clay	13.4	89	—	—	—
1.6-3.7	Silty sand	22.0	—	31	—	—
3.7-4.8	Clayey sandy silt	21.6	8	—	5.6	78
4.8-5.9	Silty/clayey sand	22.0	—	29	—	—
5.9-7.9	Sandy silty clay	21.0	—	—	—	—
7.9-8.7	Silty/clayey sand	22.0	—	29	—	—
8.7-11.7	Silty clay	20.1	19	—	3.2	220
11.7-12.8	Clayey silt	20.6	10	—	1.9	320
12.8-14.6	Silty clay	21.9	9	—	4.9	103
14.6-17.0	Clayey silt	21.6	10	—	2.0	292
17.0-18.4	Very dense silt	21.0	—	30	—	—

Note: z = depth from the ground surface, γ_m = unit weight, PI = plasticity index, OCR = overconsolidation ratio, ϕ_c = critical-state friction angle, and s_u = undrained shear strength.

^a The layer thicknesses correspond to the location of the H-pile load test. For the layer thicknesses at the location of the CEP pile load test, refer to Kim et al. (2009).

The test piles consisted of a steel H-pile (HP 310×110, with flange width b_f of 310 mm, section depth d of 308 mm, and flange and web thicknesses, t_f and t_w , of 15 mm), and a closed-ended, steel, pipe pile (with an outer diameter B of 356 mm and a wall thickness of 12.7 mm). Both piles were driven using an ICE-42S single-acting diesel hammer, with a ram weight of 18.2 kN and a maximum hammer stroke of 3.13 m, down to a depth of 17.4 m from the ground surface. The bases of both piles were embedded in the very dense silt layer by a vertical distance of at least $1.5B$ for the CEP pile and $1.5b_f$ for the H-pile. The horizontal distance between the H-pile and the CEP pile was 7.32 m.

The shaft of the CEP pile was instrumented with 17

pairs of VW strain gauges, while the flanges of the H-pile were instrumented with 12 pairs of VW strain gauges. The gauges were spot-welded to the pile surface and covered with a semi-circular plate; the openings of the cover plate were sealed with silicone rubber. In addition, the gauges were covered with steel angle channels (76 mm wide and 6 mm thick) welded to the pile surface; this was done to protect the gauges during pile driving. The cables from the strain gauges were routed to the ground surface through the steel channels and then connected to the data acquisition system. The Young's modulus of both piles was determined from the data obtained from the VW strain gauges installed on the portion of the pile shaft located above the ground surface. Detailed installation steps for these strain gauges can be found in Bica et al. (2014).

Fig. 3. q_c profiles at the H-pile test site in Jasper County, Indiana (after Seo et al., 2009).

Two slow-maintained SLTs were performed on both the CEP pile and the H-pile. For the CEP pile, the SLTs were performed 50 days and 90 days after pile driving, whereas for the H-pile, the SLTs were performed 63 days and 99 days after pile driving. The load Q applied on the pile head was measured by a load cell, while the settlement w of the pile head was measured by two dial gauges (one on each side of the pile) attached to two reference beams. The H-pile and the CEP pile were loaded in increments of 178 kN and 178–356 kN, respectively. For each load increment ΔQ , the pile head settlements were recorded at different values of time (i.e., at 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 80, 100 and 120 min). Each load increment was maintained until the settlement rate from two consecutive settlement readings at the pile head was less than 0.5 mm/hr. However, when it took longer than 2 hrs to satisfy this settlement rate criterion, the next load increment was applied after the difference

in settlement rates between the current and previous records was less than 5%. As the load applied on the pile head approached the plunging or limit load Q_L , the load increment was decreased to 45–89 kN and 89–134 kN for the CEP pile and H-pile, respectively. After reaching the plunging load, the piles were unloaded in 356-kN-load steps.

For the CEP pile, the ultimate load Q_{ult} corresponding to a pile head settlement w of $0.1B$ (35.6 mm) was 1345 kN and 1500 kN from SLT-1 and SLT-2, respectively, with shaft and base capacities (without correction for residual load) of 946 kN and 399 kN, respectively, from SLT-1, and 1066 kN and 434 kN, respectively, from SLT-2. Residual loads could not be measured accurately due to drifts in the zero readings of the VW strain gauges observed after pile driving. CAPWAP predictions based on DLT-1 performed at the end of initial driving of the CEP test pile indicated shaft, base, and total capacities of 195 kN, 710 kN, and 905 kN, respectively; the pile set was 4.3 mm ($0.012B$). A restrrike test (DLT-2) was performed 127 days later on reaction pile RCEP-1, which was identical to the CEP test pile and driven to the same depth as the CEP test pile. CAPWAP predictions based on DLT-2 indicated shaft, base, and total capacities of 1379 kN, 873 kN, and 2252 kN, respectively; the pile set was 5 mm ($0.014B$). Detailed results of the DLTs and setup effects for all piles (including the reaction piles) tested at this site can be found in Lee et al. (2010).

Fig. 4. Comparison of q_{sl} profiles obtained from the first CEP pile load test (not correcting for residual load) in Jasper County, Indiana, with those predicted using (a) PPDM, (b) ICPDM, (c) UWAPDM, (d) NGIPDM, and (e) FPDM (Han et al., 2017).

Fig. 4 compares the limit unit shaft resistance q_{sl} profile of the CEP pile obtained from SLT-1 with those predicted using different CPT-based pile design methods. Except for the FPDM, the pile design methods predict the q_{sl} profile of the CEP pile reasonably well. Table 5 compares the ultimate base capacity $Q_{b,ult}$ of the CEP pile obtained from SLT-1 with those predicted by the pile design methods. The ratio of the value of $Q_{b,ult}$ predicted by the design methods to that obtained from SLT-1 ranged from 3.5–5.1; this was due to the embedment of the pile base in a thin layer of very dense silt with high q_c (≈ 50 MPa) underlain by a thick layer of soft silty clay with low q_c (≈ 1.5 MPa).

Table 5. Comparison between predicted and measured base capacities of CEP pile in Jasper County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2017, 2019c).

Test/design method	Value (kN)
SLT-1 ($w = 0.1B$)	399 ^a
PPDM	1416
ICPDM	1694
UWAPDM	2023
NGIPDM	1421
FPDM	1557

^aNot corrected for residual load.

Table 6 compares the measured SLT capacity of the CEP pile with capacities predicted using different pile driving formulas available in the literature. The ultimate load capacity Q_{ult} of the pile estimated using the Salgado et al. (2017b) formula is 1280 kN, which is 5% smaller than that obtained from SLT-1. The mobilized static pile resistance from CAPWAP (based on a restrrike test performed 35 days after end of driving on an identical neighboring pile) was 1486 kN; the pile set was 3.6 mm

($0.01B$). The Gates and PCUBC formulas also produce close estimates of pile capacity, with a difference of about 20% compared to that obtained from SLT-1. However, the ratios of the pile capacity estimated by the Janbu, Danish, and Modified ENR formulas to that obtained from SLT-1 are about 1.4, 1.7, and 2.4, respectively.

Table 6. Comparison between measured SLT capacity and capacities predicted using pile driving formulas for CEP pile in Jasper County, Indiana (after Salgado et al., 2017b).

Test/pile driving formula	Value (kN)
SLT-1 ($w = 0.1B$)	1345
Salgado et al. (2017b) formula ($w = 0.1B$)	1280
CAPWAP	1486 ^a
Gates formula	1050
Modified ENR formula	3277
Danish formula	2289
PCUBC formula	1609
Janbu formula	1840

^aBased on a restrike test performed not on the CEP test pile but on an identical neighboring pile 35 days after the end of driving.

Table 7. Comparison between predicted and measured capacities of H-pile in Jasper County, Indiana (after Seo et al., 2009).

Test/design method	t (days)	Shaft (kN)	Base (kN)	Total (kN)
DLT-1 ^a	0	311	679	990
SLT-1 ($w = 0.1B_{eq}$) ^b	63	933	906	1839
SLT-2 ($w = 0.1B_{eq}$) ^b	99	958	893	1851
DLT-2 ^a	126	479	1007	1486
NGIPDM	100 ^c	1281	1096	2377
ICPDM ^d	—	1228	853	2081

Note: t = time after initial driving of the test pile, and B_{eq} = equivalent circular H-pile diameter (= 349 mm).

^aPile set = 7.1 mm ($\approx 0.02B_{eq}$) for DLT-1 and 14.5 mm ($\approx 0.04B_{eq}$) for DLT-2.

^bNot accounting for residual loads.

^cThe value corresponds to the prediction of pile capacity in clay.

^dFor piles in clay, the method is intended to estimate the shaft resistance after dissipation of the excess pore water pressure generated during pile installation.

Table 7 compares the pile capacities obtained from the SLTs and DLTs performed on the H-pile with those predicted using different CPT-based pile design methods. According to the CAPWAP pile capacity calculations, the total capacity of the H-pile increased by 50% from the end of initial driving to the beginning of a restrike performed 126 days later; this was due to an increase of 54% in the shaft capacity and 48% in the base capacity. The ICPDM and NGIPDM overpredicted the value of Q_{sL} by 32% and 37%, respectively, but predictions of $Q_{b,ult}$ were closer to the value obtained from SLT-1, with a difference of 6% and 21% for the ICPDM and NGIPDM, respectively. As discussed by Seo et al. (2009), the improved estimates of $Q_{b,ult}$ for the H-pile were due to the use of a representative cone resistance q_{cb} (24 MPa) in pile base capacity calculations that considered both the relative resistances of the strong

(very dense silt) and weak (soft silty clay) layers as well as the vertical distance from the pile base to the interface between the strong and weak layers following the procedure of Xu and Lehane (2008). The use of a simple cone resistance averaging scheme, such as taking the average of the q_c values over a vertical distance of 1.0–1.5 B above the pile base and 1.5–2.0 B below the pile base, to determine the value of q_{cb} should be done with caution, particularly when a weak soil layer is present near the pile base.

3.3 Marshall County, Indiana

Table 8 summarizes the properties of the soil layers at the test site in Marshall County; the soil profile consists primarily of layers of medium-dense-to-dense silty sand and stiff-to-hard silt and sand mixtures. The minimum residual friction angle $\phi_{r,min}$, sensitivity S_t , overconsolidation ratio (OCR), and undrained shear strength s_u of the silty clay layer are 12°, 2.62, 5.3, and 200 kPa, respectively. The groundwater table was located at a depth of 4.3 m below the ground surface. Layers of silt with sand were classified as "sand" for the purpose of pile capacity analysis because the silt was non-plastic. Fig. 5 shows the q_c profiles obtained from two CPT soundings, C1 and C2, performed at a distance of 3–12 m from the test pile location.

Table 8. Soil profile at the test site in Marshall County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2017).

z (m)	Layer description	wc (%)	γ_m (kN/m ³)	ϕ_c (°)	δ_c (°)
0.0-3.4	Stiff to very stiff silt with sand	14.8	19.4	33	29.7
3.4-5.2	Medium-dense silty sand	13.4	21.2	33	29.7
5.2-9.1	Dense sand	10.5	20.7	33	29.7
9.1-10.5	Silty clay	14.7	21.5	24	20.0
10.5-12.8	Dense sand	10.5	20.7	33	29.7
12.8-24.7	Hard silt with sand	10.8	20.7	33	29.7

Note: z = depth from the ground surface, wc = water content, γ_m = unit weight, ϕ_c = critical-state friction angle, and δ_c = critical-state interface friction angle.

The test pile was a closed-ended, steel, pipe pile with an outer diameter B of 356 mm and a wall thickness of 9.53 mm. The pile was driven using a single-acting impact hammer (APE model D30-32), with a ram weight of 29.4 kN and a maximum hammer stroke of 3.2 m, down to a depth of 15.42 m from the ground surface. The base of the pile was embedded in the hard silt with sand layer. The pile shaft was instrumented with 12 pairs of VW strain gauges and 9 pairs of ER strain gauges.

DLTs with the pile driving analyzer (PDA) were performed on the test pile both at the end of initial driving and during a restrike test 22 days after the initial driving. Two strain transducers and two piezoelectric accelerometers were installed on opposite sides of the outer surface of the test pile. The ultimate capacities of the pile were estimated from the DLTs using the signal matching program CAPWAP.

Fig. 5. q_c profiles at the test site in Marshall County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2017).

A slow-maintained SLT was performed on the test pile 9 days after the end of initial driving. A hydraulic jack was used to apply a static load on the pile head, and the applied load was measured using a load cell. The pile head settlement w was measured by two digital deflectometers placed on diametrically opposite sides of the test pile head and supported on reference beams. The pile was initially loaded in increments of 178–222 kN up to a load level of 1868 kN. After that, the load increment was decreased to 111 kN until the plunging or limit load Q_L was reached. Each load increment was maintained until the settlement rate calculated from two consecutive pile head settlement readings was less than 0.5 mm/hr. Further details of the loading and unloading schedules can be found in Han et al. (2017).

From the SLT results, the ultimate load Q_{ult} corresponding to a pile head settlement w of $0.1B$ (35.6 mm) was 3275 kN, whereas the load Q_L and pile head settlement required for the pile to start plunging into the ground were 3394 kN and 48.3 mm ($0.136B$), respectively. Since the readings obtained from VW strain gauges are susceptible to zero drift, the residual loads were measured using the data obtained only from the ER strain gauges.

Table 9 compares the pile capacities obtained from the static and dynamic load tests performed on the test pile with those predicted using different CPT-based pile design methods. The maximum pile head settlement induced by the final blow in the restrike test (DLT-2) was 24 mm ($\approx 0.07B$). According to the CAPWAP pile capacity calculations, the total pile capacity increased by 74% from the end of initial driving to the restrike test performed 22 days later; this was due to an increase in the pile shaft and base capacities by 140% and 32%, respectively. The PPDM, ICPDM, and UWAPDM

provided the best estimates of Q_{ult} , with a difference of 4% or less compared to the value obtained from the SLT.

Table 9. Comparison between predicted and measured capacities of CEP pile in Marshall County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2017; Sakleshpur et al., 2021b).

Test/design method	t (days)	Shaft (kN)	Base (kN)	Total (kN)
DLT-1	0	752	1179	1931
SLT ($w = 0.1B$) ^a	9	2344	931	3275
SLT ($w = 0.1B$) ^b	9	2045	1230	3275
DLT-2	22	1807	1560	3367
PPDM	—	1926	1248	3174
NGIPDM	—	2410	1157	3567
ICPDM	10 ^c	1933	1208	3141
UWAPDM	10–20 ^c	1909	1443	3352
FPDM	≈ 10 ^c	1762	1312	3074

Note: t = time after initial driving of the test pile.

^a Not corrected for residual loads.

^b After correction for residual loads.

^c The value corresponds to the prediction of pile capacity in sandy soil.

Table 10 compares the measured SLT capacity of the CEP pile with capacities predicted using different pile driving formulas available in the literature. The pile capacities estimated by the Salgado et al. (2017b) formula, CAPWAP (DLT-2), and the Danish formula are in good agreement with the measured SLT capacity of the pile; the difference is less than 5%. In contrast, the pile capacity estimated by the Modified ENR formula is about 2.7 times that obtained from the SLT. The Janbu, PCUBC, and Gates formulas underestimate the pile capacity by 16%, 23%, and 55%, respectively.

Table 10. Comparison between measured SLT capacity and capacities predicted using pile driving formulas for CEP pile in Marshall County, Indiana (after Salgado et al., 2017b).

Test/pile driving formula	Value (kN)
SLT ($w = 0.1B$)	3275
Salgado et al. (2017b) formula ($w = 0.1B$)	3300
CAPWAP	3367
Gates formula	1490
Modified ENR formula	8679
Danish formula	3445
PCUBC formula	2537
Janbu formula	2752

3.4 Tippecanoe County, Indiana

Table 11 summarizes the properties of the soil layers at the test site in Tippecanoe County; the soil profile consists primarily of layers of poorly-graded sand and gravel mixtures, which is typical of outwash geologic regions in Indiana. Outwash is a sorted and stratified mixture of sand and gravel particles transported and deposited by glacial meltwater (Sakleshpur et al., 2021a). The coefficient of curvature C_c of the soil layers ranges from 0.6–0.9. The particle roundness R (Wadell, 1932) and particle sphericity S (Wadell, 1933) of the layers containing sand-gravel mixtures are in the range

of 0.41–0.50 and 0.81–0.84, respectively. The groundwater table was located at a depth of 3.05 m below the ground surface.

Table 11. Soil profile at the test site in Tippecanoe County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2019a,b, 2020a,b).

z (m)	Layer description	γ_m (kN/m ³)	D_{50} (mm)	GC (%)	C_U (—)	ϕ_c (°)	δ_c (°)
0.0-5.5	Clayey silt with sand	19.5	—	0	3.0	30	24.6
5.5-8.2	Sand with gravel	20.0	0.4	4	2.6	32	26.2
8.2-10.4	Sandy gravel	21.5	4.5	49	34.6	35	23.1
10.4-16.8	Sand with gravel	20.0	0.9	10	4.8	32	24.3
16.8-22.6	Gravelly sand	21.5	4.1	43	16.6	34	23.1
22.6-32.6	Gravelly sand	21.5	1.1	28	8.3	33	25.1

Note: z = depth from the ground surface, γ_m = unit weight, D_{50} = mean particle size, GC = gravel content, C_U = coefficient of uniformity, ϕ_c = critical-state friction angle, and δ_c = critical-state interface friction angle.

Fig. 6. q_c profile at the test site in Tippecanoe County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2019a,b, 2020a,b).

Fig. 6 shows the q_c profile obtained from a CPT sounding performed at a distance of about 3.7 m from the test pile location. Due to the high gravel content of the soil layers at the site, a drill-and-push scheme was used to obtain the complete cone resistance profile. This scheme consisted of pushing a 44.5-mm-diameter cone through a hollow stem auger that was used to drill through the hard layers (Ganju et al., 2020). The assumed q_c distribution in Fig. 6 corresponds to those depths where drilling was in operation.

A closed-ended, steel, pipe pile and an open-ended, steel, pipe pile were tested side-by-side at the site; the center-to-center distance between them was 7.31 m. The CEP pile had an outer diameter B of 610 mm and a wall thickness of 13 mm. The OEP pile was composed of two segments, a bottom segment and a top segment, each of length equal to 18.3 m. The bottom segment is a double-

wall system consisting of an outer pipe with an outer diameter B of 660 mm and an inner pipe with an outer diameter of 584 mm; both pipes have the same wall thickness of 13 mm. The gap between the outer pipe and the cutting shoe (welded to the bottom of the inner pipe) was filled with silicone, resulting in a final wall thickness (or annulus thickness) of 51 mm. The top segment of the pile has the same outer diameter as that of the bottom segment but a wall thickness of 19 mm.

The CEP pile was driven using a single-acting diesel hammer (APE model D70-52), with a ram weight of 68.7 kN and a maximum hammer stroke of 3.4 m, down to a depth of 17.37 m from the ground surface. The final embedment depth of the CEP pile, however, was 17.68 m due to the addition of 0.3 m of sandy backfill material in order to raise the ground surface. For installation of the OEP pile, a steel casing with a diameter of 0.91 m was first installed from the ground surface up to a depth of 8.53 m. The soil inside the casing was excavated prior to driving the two segments of the OEP pile; thus, pile driving started from a depth of 8.53 m and not from the ground surface. This was done because the heads of the production piles for the Sagamore Parkway bridge were to be located at a depth of 8.53 m below the ground surface to avoid problems related to potential scour/erosion at the site. The bottom segment of the OEP pile, with the inner and outer pipes connected, was lowered into the 0.91-m-diameter hole and driven into the ground up to a depth of 16.8 m using the same driving system as that used to install the CEP pile. Three days later, the top segment of the OEP pile was welded to the bottom segment and driven into the ground until the pile base reached a final depth of 30.48 m from the ground surface.

Fig. 7. Profiles of IFR and soil plug length measured during driving of the OEP pile at the test site in Tippecanoe County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2020a,b).

Fig. 7 shows the profiles of the IFR and the soil plug length measured during driving of the OEP pile. Details of the weight system used to measure the development of the soil plug during driving of the OEP pile are presented in Han et al. (2020a). The value of IFR decreased from 92% at the start of driving to 70% at the end of driving of the OEP pile. The value of the PLR at the end of driving was 77.7%. After pile driving, the gap between the casing and the OEP pile was backfilled with loose pea gravel to prevent lateral instability during the SLT.

The shaft of the CEP pile was instrumented with 12 pairs of VW strain gauges and 20 pairs of ER strain gauges. For the double-wall OEP pile, the shaft of the inner pipe of the bottom segment was instrumented with 19 pairs of ER strain gauges, the shaft of the outer pipe of the bottom segment was instrumented with 11 pairs of VW strain gauges and 14 pairs of ER strain gauges, and the shaft of the top segment of the pile was instrumented with 3 pairs of VW strain gauges and 5 pairs of ER strain gauges. More details about the pile instrumentation can be found in Ganju et al. (2020) and Han et al. (2020a).

Two DLTs with the PDA were performed on the CEP pile: one at the end of initial driving and the other at the beginning of a restrike 22 days after the initial driving. In addition, two DLTs were also performed on the OEP pile: one at the end of initial driving and the other at the beginning of a restrike 15 days after the initial driving. Slow-maintained SLTs were performed on the OEP pile and CEP pile 8 days and 13 days, respectively, after pile driving. Details of the slow-maintained loading schedule and load increment size can be found in Han et al. (2020a,b) and Ganju et al. (2020). For the OEP pile, the ultimate load Q_{ult} corresponding to a pile head settlement w of $0.1B$ (66 mm) was 4782 kN, whereas the load Q_L and pile head settlement required for the pile to start plunging into the ground were 6228 kN and 149 mm ($0.225B$), respectively. For the CEP pile, the value of Q_{ult} at $w = 0.1B$ (61 mm) was 4559 kN, whereas the load Q_L and pile head settlement required for the pile to start plunging into the ground were 5449 kN and 129 mm ($0.21B$), respectively.

Table 12 and Table 13 compare the pile capacities obtained from the static and dynamic load tests performed on the OEP pile and CEP pile, respectively, with those predicted using different CPT-based pile design methods. For the CEP pile, the pile head settlement induced by the last blow at the end of driving (DLT-1) was 10 mm ($\approx 0.016B$), whereas the pile head settlement at restrike (DLT-2) was 5 mm ($\approx 0.008B$). According to the CAPWAP pile capacity calculations, the total capacity of the CEP pile increased by 10% from the end of initial driving to the beginning of a restrike performed 22 days later; this was due to an increase of 25% in the shaft capacity and a reduction of 2% in the base capacity. The total capacity of the OEP pile increased by 8% from the end of initial driving to the

beginning of a restrike performed 15 days later; this was due to a reduction of 28% in the shaft capacity and an increase of 74% in the base capacity.

Table 12. Comparison between predicted and measured capacities of OEP pile in Tippecanoe County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2020a,b; Sakleshpur et al., 2021b).

Test/design method	t (days)	Shaft (kN)	Plug (kN)	Annulus (kN)	Base (kN)	Total (kN)
DLT-1	0	1459	—	—	778	2237
SLT ($w = 0.1B$) ^a	8	2562	356	1864	2220	4782
SLT ($w = 0.1B$) ^b	8	2264	312	2206	2518	4782
DLT-2	15	1050	—	—	1356	2406
PPDM	—	2397	—	—	2432	4829
ICPDM	10	4820	—	—	2218	7038
UWAPDM	10-20	4261	—	—	2620	6881

Note: t = time after initial driving of the test pile. The base resistance of the pile obtained from the SLT is equal to the sum of the plug and annulus resistances.

^a Not corrected for residual loads.

^b After correction for residual loads.

Table 13. Comparison between predicted and measured capacities of CEP pile in Tippecanoe County, Indiana (after Ganju et al., 2020; Sakleshpur et al., 2021b).

Test/design method	t (days)	Shaft (kN)	Base (kN)	Total (kN)
DLT-1	0	939	1246	2185
SLT ($w = 0.1B$) ^a	13	2389	2170	4559
SLT ($w = 0.1B$) ^b	13	2156	2403	4559
DLT-2	22	1170	1223	2393
PPDM	—	1814	4321	6135
ICPDM	10	2056	3618	5674
UWAPDM	10-20	2624	5028	7653
NGIPDM	—	3664	3815	7479
FPDM	10	3168	4204	7372

Note: t = time after initial driving of the test pile.

^a Not corrected for residual loads.

^b After correction for residual loads.

Since the CEP and OEP piles were driven into a soil profile with high gravel content, a lower-bound profile of cone resistance (Fig. 8), drawn approximately through the valleys of the actual q_c profile, was considered in the estimation of pile capacity using CPT-based pile design methods (Ganju et al., 2020; Han et al., 2020a,b). For the OEP pile, the shaft capacity predicted by the PPDM is in good agreement with that obtained from the SLT after correction for residual loads; however, the ICPDM and UWAPDM overpredicted the shaft capacity of the OEP pile by a factor of 2. All three design methods (PPDM, ICPDM, and UWAPDM) produced good estimates of base capacity because (a) most (87.6%) of the OEP pile's base resistance came from the annulus resistance, and (b) the measured cone resistance is representative of the pile's annulus resistance due to the comparable values of the cone diameter (44.5 mm) and the annulus (wall) thickness (51 mm) of the pile. The NGIPDM and FPDM do not account for the effect of soil plugging (i.e., IFR and PLR) during the installation of an OEP pile.

Fig. 8. Lower-bound q_c profile for estimation of pile capacity at the test site in Tippecanoe County, Indiana (after Han et al., 2019a, 2020a).

Table 14. Comparison between predicted and measured base capacities of CEP pile in Tippecanoe County, Indiana (after Ganju et al., 2020).

Test/design method	Base capacity (kN)
DLT-1	1246
SLT ($w = 0.1B$) ^a	2170
SLT ($w = 0.1B$) ^b	2403
DLT-2	1223
PPDM	2340
ICPDM	3039
UWAPDM	1824
NGIPDM	2006
FPDM	2523

Note: For the pile design methods, the base capacities were recalculated assuming that the representative cone resistance q_{cb} near the pile base is equal to the limit unit base resistance q_{bL} of the pile obtained from the SLT.

^a Not corrected for residual loads.

^b After correction for residual loads.

The PPDM, ICPDM, and UWAPDM predicted the shaft capacity of the CEP pile reasonably well, with the ICPDM just 5% below the value obtained from the SLT after correction for residual loads. However, the base capacity of the CEP pile was overpredicted by the design methods due to the high gravel content of the soil layer in which the pile base was embedded; the closest estimate was provided by the ICPDM, which was still 51% greater than the value obtained from the SLT after correction for residual loads. The high cone resistance q_{cb} (28.7 MPa) measured near the base of the CEP pile may be unrealistic because of the particle scale effect on q_c (i.e., the effect of the relative size of the cone with respect to the size of the gravel particles). Given that the limit unit base resistance q_{bL} of a CEP pile is generally

comparable to q_{cb} (Salgado, 2022), the base capacity of the CEP pile may be recalculated assuming the value of q_{cb} to be equal to that of q_{bL} (10.4 MPa). Table 14 shows that the base capacity of the CEP pile predicted by the CPT-based pile design methods, considering $q_{cb} = q_{bL}$, is now closer to that obtained from the SLT after correction for residual loads.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Four well-documented case histories of static and dynamic load tests performed on fully instrumented, driven piles (closed-ended pipe piles, open-ended pipe piles, and H-piles) in multilayered soil profiles were presented. The instrumentation scheme consisted of a dense arrangement of electrical-resistance and vibrating-wire strain gauges installed on diametrically opposite sides of the pile shaft and along the entire length of the shaft. This allowed the separation of the total capacity of the pile into the shaft and base components. In addition, the open-ended pipe piles consisted of a double-wall system and were instrumented in a way that allowed the separation of the base resistance into the plug and annulus resistances. Electrical-resistance strain gauges are generally more suitable for measuring the residual loads locked in the pile at the end of driving than vibrating-wire strain gauges, which may be subjected to potentially significant drifts in the zero readings. However, vibrating-wire strain gauges are resistant to moisture intrusion and are thus more suitable for long-term monitoring of foundation response than electrical-resistance strain gauges.

The pile capacities predicted using five CPT-based pile design methods (PPDM, ICPDM, UWAPDM, NGIPDM, and FPDM) were compared with those obtained from the results of the static load tests and dynamic load tests (using the pile driving analyzer and the signal matching program CAPWAP). Pile capacity estimates obtained from the analysis of DLT data at the end of initial driving tend to be conservative when compared to those obtained from static load test results. Among the pile design methods, the PPDM, ICPDM, and UWAPDM provided the most accurate estimates of the ultimate load capacity of the pile for the case histories considered in this paper. However, estimation of pile base capacity should be done with caution when the pile base is embedded in a very dense silty or sandy layer of limited thickness overlying a softer or much looser soil layer. Current CPT-based pile design methods tend to overestimate the capacity of piles driven in gravelly soils. For piles installed in soils with high gravel content, a lower-bound profile of cone resistance (avoiding the sharp peaks in q_c likely caused by the cone striking a large gravel particle) should be used as input in the estimation of pile capacity.

The pile capacities predicted using six pile driving formulas [Gates, Modified ENR, Danish, PCUBC, and Salgado et al. (2017b) formulas] were also compared

with those obtained from the results of the static load tests. Among the pile driving formulas, the Salgado et al. (2017b) formulas provided the most accurate estimates of pile capacity for the case histories considered in this paper.

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